

Value Creation in Digital Serious Games for Online Corporate Training: A Qualitative Analysis

Mathias Freire de Carvalho¹
¹Rennes School of Business, France

Abstract

Online Corporate Training (OCT) services are experiencing growth due to digital transformation, addressing the need for up-skilling and organizational competitiveness. This article examines value creation (VC) in digital serious games (SG) for OCT by analyzing relationships among B2B actors, particularly within emerging markets. Utilizing a qualitative methodology, the study conducted n=27 semi-structured interviews with Brazilian serious games developers and identified key drivers of VC in inter- and intraorganizational interactions that shape the deployment of SGs. Findings reveal that the value perceptions of serious games developers (SGDs) and client organizations (COs) significantly influence the success of SG-based OCTs, highlighting areas for improvement in communication and training processes, and positioning SGs as tools for lifelong learning and strategic enhancement in client organizations.

Keywords: *Digital Serious Games, Online Corporate Training, Brazil, Value Creation.*

Introduction

In recent years, skilled labor shortages have significantly hindered global economic recovery, particularly following the COVID-19 crisis (Statista, 2022). Retaining employees through continuous training has become crucial in HR (Tenakwah, 2021). The WEF predicts that over the next decade, 1.1 billion jobs could be radically transformed by technology (WEF, 2022, p. 1). Quiet Quitting (QQ) is increasingly seen as a global issue and a symptom of poor management (Harter, 2022, p. 1). Similarly, the Great Resignation (GR) reflects a misalignment between employee expectations and the realities of the workplace, leading qualified workers to leave their jobs (Liu, 2022). Previous studies refer to the necessity of deepening such concepts (Carvalho, 2022), which could trigger a 'Great Reskilling' phenomenon, necessitating a strategic shift in workforce retention (Kis, 2022). As Millennials and Gen-Zers become the majority in the workforce, their influence on human-centered training may exacerbate global workforce demand, contrasting with shrinking employee supply and necessitating more efficient, technology-driven interactions (Wadley, 2021). To enhance employee retention, Human Resources Management (HRM) must prioritize diverse and committed approaches, emphasizing quality training content, optimized pedagogical design, and innovative technology applications (Johnson, 2020; Strack et al., 2021). However, the success factors for online corporate training (OCT) are no longer clear-cut, leaving many organizations unable to meet their advanced training needs solely with in-house expertise. At the same time, specialized outsourcing introduces new challenges and risks (Kimiloglu et al., 2017).

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The Serious Games (SG) global market signals growth (Mordor, 2020). Digital training applications, following transformative environmental trends (Gegenfurtner et al., 2020), are deployed across many industries, such as automotive (Witt et al., 2011), consultancy (Donovan, 2012), and cosmetics (Allal-Chérif & Bidan, 2017). Compared to traditional OCT alternatives' setup and logistics, digital SGs often reduce time and costs (Pillai et al., 2018) while enabling performance assessment and real-time adaptability in training goals (Carvalho et al., 2014). SGs are recognized as highly engaging (Imlig-Iten e Petko, 2018), notably offering intricate dynamics that combine game design, storytelling, aesthetics, and pedagogical strategies (Linderoth e Sjöblom, 2019).

SG scholars have primarily focused on taxonomy, specific fields, and industry applications, structural and pedagogical design (Göbel, 2016; Wilkinson, 2016), often aiming at classifying what games are, how they are developed, where they are deployed, and in what context they are used, often reflecting mature markets' conditions (Korhonen et al., 2019). As SG research focuses primarily on 'gamers' (i.e., employees) and 'investors' (top and middle organizational decision makers), outsourced Serious Games Developers (SGD) roles are seldom studied (Zuñiga-Collazos et al., 2019), as is their role and influence on COs' business strategy, which remains understudied, despite likely exerting a significant impact on SG-based training tactics and development (Pérez & Cambra-Fierro, 2015). This gap encourages a better understanding of SG co-development dynamics, unpacking the Business-to-Business (B2B) practices between SGDs and COs (Gupta et al., 2022).

The global Serious Games (SG) market is growing (Mordor, 2020). Digital training applications, driven by transformative trends (Gegenfurtner et al., 2020), are used across industries such as automotive, consultancy, and cosmetics (Witt et al., 2011; Donovan, 2012; Allal-Chérif & Bidan, 2017). Compared to traditional OCT methods, digital SGs often reduce time and costs (Pillai & Sivathanu, 2018) while enhancing performance assessment and allowing real-time adaptability in training (Carvalho et al., 2014). SGs are highly engaging, offering complex dynamics that integrate game design, storytelling, and pedagogical strategies (Imlig-Iten & Petko, 2018; Linderoth & Sjöblom, 2019), reflecting organizational cultural shifts (Westerman et al., 2014).

Literature Review

Online Corporate Training and Technology

The Online Corporate Training (OCT) literature encompasses many areas, such as e-corporate knowledge development, e-upskilling, e-performance, employee engagement, etc. (Appelbaum et al., 2017). The definition of an 'online training program', who needs to be trained and on what remains an ongoing debate, as fast-pacing technology influences how OCT is conceptualized and institutionalized (Subramanian e Zimmermann, 2020). Technology affordability and access are also noted to increasingly generate new B2B realities for actors' lifelong learning (Dahou et al., 2019). The gaming industry is fast evolving into 'Gaming-as-a-Service' – expected to represent US\$ 7 billion by 2027 (Karnes, 2021). OCTs rely on several coexisting 'learning management system' (LMS) formats, centered at institutionalized (re)upskilling training investments (Devarakonda, 2019). SGs are defined as a highly interactive 'educational, gamified system', enabling learning experimentation and experiences (Ahmed e Sutton, 2017) through iterative, highly engaging user interfaces (UI), encapsulated by hedonic characteristics, where the 'journey is deemed as important as the outcome' (Abt, 1987). They support less straightforward diffusion strategies, reflecting the workforce's diversity (Bekmanova et al., 2021).

Research has provided many insights on SG pedagogical factors towards skill development, low imitability and transferability, while taking the outsourced SGD role for granted (Maia et al., 2020). In agreement with Turnbull et al. (1996), network effects impact the supplier–buyer dyadic interactions,

transforming them into more complex behavior patterns, guiding (B2B) actor exchanges. SGD's competitiveness is linked by their inherent 'Client Organization (CO) relationship skillset', contextualized by preexisting iterative behavior patterns formed by previous SG selling and buying outcomes (or lack thereof). Formed by SGD and CO actor interplay, these networks are under (more or less) specific behavior guidelines guiding SG sales pitches, development, deployment, and assessment phases, as part of an ecosystem. Nonetheless, SGDs' participation and influence remain understudied (Martins et al., 2019). Taken together, we identify a yet underexplored research gap, as no study thoroughly explore SGD-CO dyadic relationships influence on SG design, mediated by CO tactics as part of broader B2B networks, encouraging reflections on how to better integrate OCT strategies as shaped by supplier-buyer relationships (Haq et al., 2018).

Online Corporate Training and Serious Games Development

SG-based training development encapsulating SGDs' capabilities and becoming increasingly relevant in establishing quality outsourced services across several industries (Ahmadi, 2020), places SGDs center stage for designing gamified training, directly related to optimum OCT medium choices (Clark et al., 2016). Nonetheless, the literature underlines the importance of constant managerial and leadership support, during both development and deployment. Conversely, CO managers looking for 'quick fix' solutions will often face a relatively high initial investment which does not translate into short term goals, denoting CO adoption readiness (Apostolopoulos, 2015). High entry costs often make customized 'training-as-a-service' SG platforms limited to larger COs, prone to enabling economies of scale and scope. SGDs, usually being Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), cater to the needs and demands of notably larger COs, informational asymmetries create additional supply hurdles for SGDs to efficiently provide services (Appelbaum et al., 2017). Intended SG-OCT outcomes may be negatively impacted, falling short of delivering competitive, co-developed HR training (Anders, 2007).

COs' readiness to adopt training SGs is underlined to depend on optimal conditions (cultural, organizational and technological) where "(...) self-confidence, [employees'] interest (...) and ease of use of eLearning platforms in predicting lifelong learning solutions, which improve business outcomes" (Malureanu et al., 2021, p. 6633). SGDs' early involvement into OCT planning ought to positively affect key aspects, such as trainee choices and system flexibility, impacting overall training efficiency and applicability (Prensky, 2001). Yet, little is known on how SGDs themselves may influence these conditions, affecting their ability to deliver customized SGs (Streicher e Smeddinck, 2016). As SG training requires specialized development, 'off the shelf' solutions may become notably less efficient, underlying the importance of enabling SGD involvement and collaboration between inter and intra organizational actors (Simons et al., 2021).

Furthermore, we note that intended benefits cannot be captured unless all actors sustainably collaborate, or co-develop (Kohtamäki e Rajala, 2016) through B2B multilevel actor interplay, jointly discovering and shaping new SG offerings (Minerbo et al., 2021). These relational approaches unfold onto a wider range of interactions (Beirão et al., 2017). In similar lines, value creation (VC) in SG-OCT initiatives leverages quality experiences, meeting individual (employee) and collective (the organization) needs and expectations (Kuppelwieser e Klaus, 2021). Such highly contextualized perceptions, based on real-world dynamics, transforms habitual value (derived from institutionalized practices) into transformational value (Blocker e Barrios, 2015).

Value is portrayed to be an outcome of actor interdependencies magnified by the proportionality of interacting network's size and complexity (Eisenmann, 2008). It is established by participating actors as resource integrators in converging and shared service ecosystems (Vargo, 2011). In the case of technologic value via innovation and product offerings, it often is the result of outsourced services risk mitigation strategies as volatile, unknown conditions persist (Iansiti e Levien, 2004). Value-based

marketing research emphasizes the quality dimension of ‘experiencing value’ in specific key aspects including needs (functional, symbolic and experiential) and beliefs (functional, social, emotional, epistemic and conditional) as driving dimensions in service ecosystems (Nasution et al., 2014).

As proposed by Macdonald et al. (2016, p. 114), value is thus defined by the: “(...) combining of supplier and customer processes and resources through a joint resource integration process to create collective and individual value in use, which is monitored and optimized through value auditing processes, reflecting new concepts such as technological innovations and the social, cultural and individual vs. group behavior influence aspects of value formation, among others.”. Evolving beyond more traditional, utilitarian and functional lenses, rooted in economic utility theory, actor exchanges unfolded beyond benefit-over-sacrifice tradeoffs, towards value through collaboration (Dodds et al., 1991). The literature suggests that such actors’ relationships can be contextualized by experience-based value creation, spread over complex service ecosystems and practices (Gebauer et al., 2013). In B2B research, the corporate environment presents multilevel, hierarchical aggregation of relationships between interorganizational actor networks, rather more complex than in consumer market exploration (Mencarelli e Rivière, 2015). In terms of experiences defining value perception, actors are continuously learning not in an individualistic manner characterized by isolated actions and reactions, but in context of previous experiences shaping future interaction behaviors and attitudes, reflected on other actors in the network who would be similarly influenced – thus enacted through social frameworks which “create social and structural (economic) bonds”, where relationships matter (Turnbull et al., 1996, p. 50).

VC is therefore not limited to exchange purchasing decision-making; it must also tend to both strategic requirements and organizational power structure. In the Interaction Approach concept, actor networks surpass exchanges of technology (e.g., product and service design, manufacture and MKTG management), defining what and where these organizations are in each marketplace by how such interactions occur. These interactions, from the supplier side, presuppose perceived utility to the buyer, mediated by motivations, thus contextualizing value (Turnbull et al., 1996). Novel OCT training tool development will inevitably affect the existing interorganizational structure (Chung et al., 2021). More to the point, in region-specific markets, VC faces distinct challenges pertaining organizational readiness (Vaitinen et al., 2018), when relationships depend on a clear resource acquisition intent – decision-makers in the organization are aware of what is needed, and how to obtain it through dyadic interactions - to be considered valuable to each party. Readiness is therefore conditioned by the organizational position in the network, providing a clear ‘current need’ perception, linked to a vision of improvement through resource acquisition. It could thus be considered a relative precondition for value – the means to reduce the gap between ‘what is’ and ‘what might be’, mediated by situated conditions. As conditions change, value can shift rapidly, influenced by significant perspective mismatches (long-term vs short-term) between actor’s individual expectations that goes beyond OCT itself (Simon, 2018). SGDs, have been markedly restrained by situated factors, impacting value actualization (Lai, 1995): inadequate offerings, poor CO strategic planning, lack of stable environmental conditions, access to technology resources, etc. (OECD, 2020). Value must consider realistic organizational engagement levels, shaped by individual, relational and/or collective expectations (Behrens, 2020). As such, current theoretical value frameworks, however discerning, do not clarify how internal and external B2B actors’ impact (and are impacted) by clustered, cross-level relationships, providing an opportunity for further exploration and investigation.

Methodology

The study adopts a constructivist, epistemological approach to explore shared human experiences within the context of service game development (SGD) research. The research aims to generate generalist

knowledge and new ideas from analyzed data through in-depth interviews with specialists, enhancing theoretical development in education and technology adoption. Interviews with n=27 SGD leaders in Brazil were conducted using semi-structured methods to obtain insights into organizational practices and market conditions. The sample, comprising predominantly graduate-educated respondents, was characterized by a flexible interview atmosphere that enabled deep inquiries. The study also integrated secondary data from industry censuses and literature to reinforce findings while employing abductive reasoning to reveal B2B relationship dynamics in this emerging market context.

Research Design

Interviews followed preestablished SSI guidelines, encouraging interviewees to volunteer their own views on key concepts, providing opportunities for more detailed topics (Mathers et al., 2000) and making each interview slightly unique.

Data Analysis Process

Based on preset topics, the phenomena were documented in a codebook (Gioia et al., 2012). Upon iterative exploration of primary and secondary data sources, data analysis promoted subjectivity richness (Spiggle, 1994) were entailed on multiple readings of the transcripts and open-ended codes, encompassing a generic and comparative revisit of secondary sources, emerging from the data and axial coding (leading to repetition), generating data categories and subcategories along the relationships to the central axis on how SGDs made sense of their role in relation to VC. Our process started with open coding, allowing us to predefine and classify emerging concepts leading to axial coding (Table 2, left column) that allows us to establish links with the extant literature, defining our final themes (aggregated codes, Table 2, right column). Supported by established literature on B2B network actors interactions, we unpacked perceptions pertaining to how 'SGDs co-create value with COs' (Abrahamsen et al., 2012), evolving into aggregated dimensions that allowed the researcher to reflect on the nature of SGD-situated practices and understand the impact they have on SG value formation, the challenges they face and market trends. Our coding produced categorization, abstraction, comparison, dimensionalities, integration, and iteration outcomes (Miles e Huberman, 1994). Consequently, a clearer view was formed of how SGDs relate to localized actions, B2B valued relationships (Kohtamäki e Rajala, 2016) and SG adoption (Oh e Yoon, 2014). Following Glaser (1978) our research went back and forth between the data and theory, matching ideas towards new knowledge.

Findings and Analysis

The data showed that Brazilian SGDs make use of social and empirical mechanisms in developing and shaping relationships with prospective COs. aiming to enhance offerings by positioning themselves as market specialists, thus preestablishing bona fides in services characterized by relative low exposure, institutionalization and formal processes. SGDs initially interacted with CO's top management, subsequently cascading towards mid-level management, although not often reaching employees for feedback. Aiming to maximize success rates, most successful SGDs were found to target organizations which could respond favorably to niche SG offerings, given prior SG experience and networking advantages. Within what was described as 'unstructured strategies and movements', the data reveal SGDs' focus on both their technical skills and COs' technology adoption capability. Seizing practices underline SGDs agentic behavior, mobilizing SGs as a viable long term OCT option. Enacting practices reflect on the tactics required to actualize new SG offerings, challenging the status quo at CO multilevel management and decision-making hierarchies. Institutionalizing practices focuses on SGDs offering legitimation, enabling OCT re-examination and promoting benefits realization. This is displayed as

(re)shaping the CO ecosystem approach to OCT. Figure 1 illustrates Second Order Code and Aggregated Dimensions (Developer interviews):

Figure 1. Second Order Code and Aggregated Dimensions (Developer interviews)

Seizing

SGDs must start off by learning what they need to promote fast sales, (re)shaping resources and tactics to support short-term, value-added transaction outcomes. Working through personal networks, SGDs attempt to maximize leads by working with internal contacts and frame subjective COs value expectations. This allows them to seize potential opportunities where timing securing prospect COs allows them to control a narrative that reflect the multiple facets of OCT needs, along multilevel exchanges. Contrasting with other more traditional OCT offerings, SGDs aim at ‘setting the stage’ by establishing market awareness of both their reputation as specialist. Respondents have realized that professional and personal networking are key, showcasing skills and previous successes while contextualizing credibility through personal market reputation.

“The sales that we make today, [brand communications happen] a lot by [WOM]; and both [my partner] and I have a good reputation in the market. So, our legacy, our experience, it already gives us 50% of that value, as we go through a sales phase”. (D12)

SGDs strive to make their SG offerings’ value explicit and self-evident, relatively to other digital and in-person training methods. It was mentioned that, although SG advantages were generally known, specifics such as personalization, agility and scalability required detailing. COs were noted to often lack the vision

to associate greater longer-term value when they felt that it was simpler (and less risky) to maintain familiar services, undervaluing SG potential benefits to organizational learning.

"We were faced with this sort of experience: a company wanted our games for recruitment and selection, loved our tool, but [in the end] chose to continue in their comfort zone, [repurchasing] their traditional [training] tool, because that already had [an established] credibility, already [provided] enough data for the firm to just stick with it". (D12)

Siloed market environments are presented as being limited by both institutional infrastructure and social barriers that frame how actors engage with (or distrust) novel technology-based offerings. SGDs lack formal negotiation and business skillsets, as most of SGDs' education is in engineering and coding, not in management and strategy. This creates informational asymmetries when dealing with COs. As such, after the initial SGs acceptance by the COs leadership, they must also be continuously promoted internally. Offerings mandated by COs' leadership are noted to not automatically be aligned and easily adopted throughout an organization, as pockets of resistance towards SGs usually persist, fostered by preexisting adversity to change and unfamiliarity, requiring a first-hand approach to cement trust and engagement.

"Our market is very amateurish. Because there are few business professionals in our market. Many of our market directors are developers who hired a lot of people, and who now think that because they became directors, CEOs, owner of the company, they think they are capable and can negotiate with clients, but it is not that. So, this makes the market amateurish, in that sense". (D06)

Nonetheless, by prioritizing short-term gains, SGDs continuously provide standard solutions ('Off-the-shelf' offerings), made available at lower prices - but with restricted degrees of customization, adapting existing systems only as needed to enable CO uniqueness perception. This constrains the market in the long run, perpetuating a negative impression of basic service provision and creativity. A similar condition occurs when COs seek the anecdotal 'magic pill solution' – expecting 100% of benefits realization with 0% engagement.

"A client looking for ways to implement solutions for [SGs], I would have to build a platform, I would have to build something, I [already] have 'this here', that I'll just customize for this case. If [other SGDs], like myself, already have something "semi-ready", this will greatly facilitate the offering of solutions". (D05)

Enacting

SGDs considered 'actionable benefits' as vital to establish value and achieve concrete results. Enacting practices legitimize SG offerings applied to COs by managing actors' expectations through iterative resources employment. Value is actualized at key exchange touchpoints, filtered by individual beliefs and biases - making it a responsibility for the SGDs to crystalize value, ranging from CO top-level management decision-makers, middle managers and potential collaborators, simultaneously enabling sustainable value and lowering potential resistance.

"So, even when [the decision maker] is [part of the leadership], he asks for the approval of [his peers]; and he asks for approval from [several other multilevel actors]; it depends on the institution, but it involves [several people], too. And [then] it's not so much about the learning, is it?". (D26)

When outsourcing SG-based OCTs, COs leadership often fail to provide interaction support long term along development and deployment phases. SGDs attempt to influence COs by proactively managing expectations with multilevel COs actors over time. Regular leadership support revalidation is required, particularly in decentralized, siloed organizational areas. Actors' value perceptions, shaped by environmental (social / organizational) experience cues, SG 'test-drives' appear to be a useful practice in providing an iterative, engaging experience, contextualized within actual CO routines. When testing SGs,

CO actors' insights on OCT applicability retrofit relevant information and realigns development, maximizing results.

"If sometimes we see [SGs] in a slightly negative way, it's not saying that we have incompetent developers per se, but it's because we have a general culture, in our country – notably, in less developed countries, this is worse in a sense - I mean, [organizations] are not quite used to gaming mechanics, so anything that seems too [foreign or] complicated will be rejected, and that even makes you wonder: " - Well, then, why make a game at all, if people don't want to play with it?" It's a difficult [value] balance, and I think the problem isn't so much with the [development] professionals, it's undoubtedly a problem with the [overall] culture towards ludic [processes]". (D15)

SGDs must regularly inform COs of completion incremental achievements, boosting trust while evidentiating change obstacles and engagement requirements, characterizing the progressive deliverance of valuable, actionable results, depicting 'proof of concept' (PoC) significance. Unlike larger COs, to SGDs - being mostly SMEs, PoCs can be very costly, thus centralizing localized collaborative development and deployment practices: SG design for specific OCT requirements in mind are set to maximize SGD control, directly enabling SG assessment controls and indirectly leveraging CO trust. It was noted that [exceedingly] long sales lead process significantly impacts how SGDs approach time and development resources – balancing investments at the cost of the the CO.

"[When I sell to a CO aiming at implementing SG solutions, I [already] have 'this here', that I'll just customize for this case. If [other SGDs], like myself, already have something "semi-ready", this will greatly facilitate the offering of solutions". (D05)

With larger, multilevel COs, OCT design adaptability must comply to internal workflows, better adhering to existing corporate culture, thus mitigating bias and enhancing SGDs training information asymmetries management. Digital SGs cater to particular OCT strategies, prompting SGDs to adapt new offerings over preexisting structures, rationalizing development cost and boosting competitiveness. This requires balanced interactions between standard and custom SG models, covering a myriad of must-have characteristics over cosmetic ones. As COs actors are influenced by both technology novelty and content appropriateness, to enact value this must be managed by SGDs.

"It would have to be created jointly [with the client], usually depending on the availability of people who could give us relevant information required for development. Adding to that, much of what is passed over to us, depending on development requirements, would need to be streamlined. It's just that, in our case, we scale content for a simulation; adapted to last four, five, six hours. Thus, we must simplify many activities and processes to be able to fit them in a short timeframe. And then, the main challenges usually are: first, availability and, second, knowing that some [training] would have to be structured differently from what [the client] is used to. [To compensate for that,] we make a little model, usually in spreadsheets, because our customization process is heavily based on calculations. So, we put together a spreadsheet, validate it with the people in charge at the company; if they say 'ok', we start to develop the software.". (D27)

Institutionalizing

SGDs endeavor to consolidate relationships by internalizing value practices, integrating COs workflows and organizational culture within the SG co-development activities and processes, enabling access and control management. SGDs described managing resources and information access to maintain realistic offering expectations, ensuring sustainable COs participation and steady feedback. Corresponding 'interactions towards value-in-use' are needed for multilevel, larger COs' internal barriers within organizational siloes, obliging SGDs to (re)shape process control to counterbalance eventual in-game inadequate behavior, while learning from CO contextualized culture. Institutionalizing baseline KPIs enables dynamic performance assessments and workplace applicability, achieved through continuous gaming data access and deployment feedback loops. SG processes and outcomes access allow SGDs to

manage interaction control, data gathering, and sustainable information flows, enabling them to gauge both individual actors and organizational value perceptions.

“[Process] transparency is also fundamental, these values of transparency help us a lot, today; you have nothing to hide from the customer. We make daily deliveries; the customer follows the milestone until it reaches its completion. Nothing is surprising to the customer. There is nothing hidden, there is no mystery”. (D10)

The effect of enabling a ‘CO perspective’ as a prerequisite for shaping expectations towards ‘problem solving’ approaches, requires a ‘best SGD fit’ strategy within overall COs evaluation systems, leveraging long term participation. SGDs reported needing to monitor and participate in what is anecdotally referred as ‘the grapevine’ (formal and informal interaction instances where personal and normative value perception are generated ‘around the game’, or in between gameplay). This can be conducted through direct or indirect conduits (game mechanics) and (in)formal actor feedback channels, directly affecting how SGDs can contribute. Failure to manage both SGs and the surrounding WOM might generate COs leadership misinterpretations. SGDs need to be aware, manage and participate in as many interactions with COs as possible. Social information inputs were considered central to future SGs engagements, constituting ‘peripheral interactions’ benefiting SGDs from early opportunity warnings - either amplifying engagement or mitigating attrition.

“(…) to be [adequately] done, there is a certain workload, especially when this workload is very high, the result is not a result that really comes from the employee [performance and expectations], it is the result that the company expects at the end and they are only seeing a [uncontextualized] number there, sometimes it's not the real numbers”. (D23)

Discussion

We aimed to analyze the impact, roles, and practices promoted by SGDs, identifying practice dynamics outlining meaningful interactions: SIZING, INTERACTING and INSTITUTIONALIZING. Turnbull et al. refer to a progressive, enduring “social and structural bond” suppliers-buyer consolidation, transforming their relationship (1996, p. 50, 51). This concept is based on Wilson and Mummalaneni’s ‘relationship cycle (RC)’ (1986), describing how suppliers harvest better value in long-term relationships, while concentrating their initial costs in early stages. In practice, because SGDs often push for standardized solutions maximizing ROI and shortening payback cycles, they remain limited to short-term interactions, where initial lead generation costs remain high, significantly reducing value capture. SGDs are thus constrained to ‘offering loops’, since buyers do not develop long-lasting commitment levels (Turnbull e Wilson, 1989). An amalgamate of factors, interactions and emotions within discussion were found to impact all actor’s state of mind and contextualize instinctive reactions and predispositions towards OCT in general and SGs in particular (Gegenfurtner et al., 2020).

In line with extant research, interorganizational communications are key to enable SGDs influence in promoting value within and across multilevel departments, especially for mid-management leaders who may feel insecure and fearful of ‘losing their grip’ when faced with new and unfamiliar situations (Almansour e Obembe, 2021). We confirm that asymmetrically evoked past negative experiences and triggered latent value destructive preconceptions towards SG-based training objectives (Shimizu, 2017) may negatively predisposed actors who cannot envision future experiences and may misunderstand SGDs interferences to positively frame expectations and outcomes. Subsequently, socially contextualized value perceptions were required as additional legitimizing efforts to conform to both socially constructed internal systems and industry culture. SGDs’ awareness (not always evident) of social institutions was key to successfully tailor value. Furthermore, resonating with the findings of Zhang et al. (2022), technology growth impacting emerging marketplaces is found to exacerbate interorganizational international conditions, influencing complex OCT initiatives, alternatively constraint, dynamize and moderate

interorganizational interplay. On a macroeconomic level, economic, political and natural conditions are found to further shaped CO culture favoring shorter term solutions over long-term relationships. SGDs themselves are affected by EM macroeconomic climate where tensions related to development costs bring about significant risk and challenges. As such, outsourced service excellence becomes secondary to cost viability. Taken together, we propose an SGD-based value framing conceptual framework, reflecting EM-based SGDs’ practices (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. SGD-Based Value Framing Conceptual Framework

Source: elaborated by the authors

Seizing Value (SV) encapsulates multiple actors’ potential acceptance of SGs amid uncertainties, where a lack of previous and consistent OCTs and SGs experience limits CO-SGs management capabilities force Brazilian SGDs to ascertain their credentials (Ozdemir et al., 2020). Newly minted interactional relationships, in agreement with current research, make SGDs were acutely concerned with gate keepers’ points of control, echoing the literature regarding how top and middle managers optimize emergent strategic vision with tacit adaptability, heavily influenced by the quality of their interplay (Vaz et al., 2021). SGDs ‘value perception is, –in most cases, impacted by past and real time multiple interactions, echoed in the literature regarding how suppliers’ past experiences influence their perception of new offers through technology-specific knowledge (Clemens, 2021). Exchanges were thus noted to aim at rapidly correct misassumptions and biases, whereby open and transparent interactions among the internal and external stakeholders was necessary to deliver identifiable outcomes. We confirm the literature concerning the amplification effect of digitization on skill development and servitization, affecting how employees train relative to organizational actor’s value perceptions (Massi et al., 2021).

Enacting Value (EnV) is encapsulated in OCT processes, realized under real life conditions, integrating novel with pre-existing organizational practices. SGDs enacting practices anchoring value when providing interactive SG experiences, generating new value insights and legitimizing them as credible sources for new technology (Ahmed e Sutton, 2017). We link EnV to SGDs value actualization aimed at supporting COs expectations, fostering leadership engagement and support for lifelong learning, subsequently enacting organizational change by leveraging SGs opt-in thus (Apostolopoulos, 2015). Agreeing with Mulcahy et al. (2018), EnV promotes learning value that stems out of technology-based training, with a moderating effect allowing for value stabilization along quick wins. EnV allows SGDs to continuously ensure a ‘best fit’ for COs’ changing needs, through (in)directly interactions with CO key decision-makers, (re)validating the offering (Garrido-López e Cai-Hillon, 2020).

Institutionalizing Value (IV), noted as SGD long-term key success factor, is in line with current research (Tuominen et al., 2020). The data shows that SGDs need to decode and adapt SG solutions towards existing COs training practices, enabling specific CO value control dynamics, and allowing a sustainable integration over time. We associate IV with SGDs efforts to impact preexisting COs institutionalized routines ('doings and sayings'), initially constituting entry barriers for novel technology while, through institutionalizing practices, becoming the norm (Bourdieu, 1984, 1992). This may be achieved through SGDs' resilience and endurance against COs resistance, subsequently allowing SGs co-creation and diffusion (Keen e Berge, 2014). IV practices became both reciprocally beneficial (to COs in the short and long term, and to SGDs in the long term), influencing existing mindsets and procedures, to develop, shape and sometime enforce the value of SGs training above (and along) other daily activities. This new reality being validated by all actors and influencers thus creating a sustainable environment towards future improvement and developments. When successful, SGDs transform themselves into expert interaction specialists facilitating SG-based OCT adoption and continuous technology-based innovation.

Research Implications

The research about digital serious games for online corporate training creates important knowledge for multiple academic disciplines which include business education psychology and technology. The research shows that serious games developers (SGDs) and client organizations (COs) base their success with SG-based OCTs on their individual value perception assessments. Research studies have demonstrated that cultural elements together with environmental conditions affect negotiation results so professionals need to develop flexible negotiation approaches (Dias, 2020a; Dias, 2020b; Dias, 2020c; Dias, 2020d). An additional implication regards research studies, which have demonstrated that empathy together with trust form essential elements for successful negotiations because they affect both negotiation results and deal-making success (Dias, 2021; Dias & Lopes, 2021; Dias, 2021a). Research has shown that nonverbal actions during negotiations create major effects on the final results (Dias, Pereira, Teles, & Lafraia, 2023; Dias, Pereira, Vieira, Barbosa, Quintão, & Lafraia, 2023). The research findings demonstrate that SGDs and COs need to establish strong relationships while managing expectations and creating trust-based environments to succeed with their SG-based OCT projects (Côrrea, Santana, & Dias, 2025; Barros & Dias, 2025). The study provides a value creation framework for SGs which businesses can use to enhance their product development and marketing efforts and deliver better customer service (Gasparini, Vieira, & Dias, 2025). The research findings about negotiation success through empathy and trust can be applied to different business environments including supply chain operations and international market activities (Dias, 2020; Dias, 2021). The research findings demonstrate that SGs function as effective tools for learning and engagement in multiple educational environments (Dias, 2023; Dias, 2023a; Dias, 2023b; Dias, 2023c; Dias, 2023d). The value creation framework for SGs enables developers to create educational games and simulations which work for K-12 students and college students. The research findings demonstrate that emotions and nonverbal signals play a crucial role in determining negotiation results and decision-making processes (Dias, Pereira, Teles, & Lafraia, 2023; Dias, Pereira, Vieira, Barbosa, Quintão, & Lafraia, 2023). The value creation framework for SGs enables developers to create mental health and well-being promotion interventions.

Future Research

Future research should study how modern technology impacts the creation of digital serious game value for corporate online training programs. The research needs to study how artificial intelligence and blockchain and virtual reality technologies influence the expansion of SGs. The research needs to

investigate how these technologies enable users to establish new interaction methods with both each other and SG-based OCT programs. Research needs to study how different cultural groups evaluate the worth of SGs relative to COs. The research would demonstrate how cultural elements affect decision processes and value assessments during SG-based OCT initiatives. The research needs to study how SGs and COs create value together in various cultural settings. Future studies should investigate how emotions influence both value evaluation and decision-making activities in SG-based OCT programs. The research investigates which emotions between excitement and frustration and boredom impact participant engagement when they use SG-based OCT programs.

Conclusion

The research shows that digital serious games (SGs) for online corporate training (OCT) value creation depends heavily on the mutual interactions between serious games developers (SGDs) and their client organizations (COs). The research demonstrates that SG-based OCT success requires knowledge about how SGs and COs establish value during their communication process. The research establishes three essential value creation elements which enable SGs to operate as permanent learning platforms for client organization strategic development. The research establishes new knowledge about B2B relationship value creation through its findings that SGs must transform their methods to fulfill changing CO requirements and develop systems for managing customer value perceptions. The research demonstrates that developers must analyze the social environment which affects their game development process. The SGD-based value framing conceptual framework helps researchers study SGD-CO relationships to discover new value creation possibilities. The framework demonstrates that SGs need to establish relationships and control expectations and establish value practices to achieve enduring business success. The research shows digital serious games create better online corporate training through business-to-business value creation in online corporate training.

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